

The European Journal of Research and Development

Volume: 1

Issue: 1

Year: 2021

**ONLINE ISSN
2822-2296**

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Scanning the Issue

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To cite this article: Oralhan, Z. (2021). Scanning the Issue. The European Journal of Research and Development, 1(1), 1-3.

Published: 31 Dec 2021.

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The current issue of The European Journal of Research and Development (Vol 1, No 1, Dec 2021) contains 5 articles.

The paper “An Approach to Innovative Raw Materials Based on Sustainability in Textile” written in Turkish language with “Tekstilde Sürdürülebilirlik ve Geri Dönüşüm Esaslı Yenilikçi Hammaddeler Üzerine Bir Yaklaşım” title in Turkish. Authors of the paper are Korhan Şen and Rengin Gürel.

The paper “Rail-Wheel Friction Management in Rail System Vehicles” written in Turkish language with “Raylı Sistem Taşıtlarında Ray-Teker Arası Sürtünme Yönetimi” title in Turkish. Author of the paper is Fatih Bezzin

The paper “Sustainable Eco-Friendly Yarns with Biodegradable Synthetic Fibers and Bringing These Fibers into Short Fiber Spinning” written in Turkish language with “Sürdürülebilir Sentetik Liflerle Çevre Dostu İpliklerin Geliştirilmesi ve Bu Liflerin Kısa Elyaf İplikçiliğine Kazandırılması” title in Turkish. Authors of the paper are Neslihan Okyay, Fatih Işık.

The paper “Investigation of Air Permeability Properties of Knitted Fabrics Obtained from Core Yarns Containing Different Core and Sheat Fibers” written in Turkish language with “Farklı Öz ve Sargı Lifleri İçeren Özlü İpliklerden Elde Edilen Örme Kumaşların Hava Geçirgenlik Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi” title in Turkish. Authors of the paper are Tuğçe Yağmur Ögüt, Kubilay Özden, Tülin Kaya Nacarkahya

The paper “Development of Method of Sheet Metal Molding to Increase Bushing and Ball Joint Pull-Out Forces” written in Turkish language with “Burç ve Rotil Çıkma Kuvvetlerinin Artırılması için Sac Kalıplama Yönteminin Geliştirilmesi” title in Turkish. Authors of the paper are Melih Tuyan and Mehmet Can Aslan